

STANDARDIZATION OF HERBAL DRUG FOENICULAM VULGARE

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ABSTRACT

The procedure of standardising herbal preparations is a key aspect of obtaining the product's quality and efficacy, and it is the rate-limiting stage in Ayurvedic formulations. The data about the concentrations employed in the formulation are provided in detail by the procedure. In this study, standardization of herbal drugs- Foeniculum vulgare was investigated. The formulary of ayurvedic drugs in India was followed in the production. For the standardisation of commercial and in-house ayurvedic medicinal products, the organoleptic qualities, physical properties, and physiological features were utilised. The drug property was evaluated and compared to the reference standards for control and quality assurance in pharmaceutical laboratories using precise and accurate metrics.

Key words- *Anti-inflammatory, physicochemical, standardization*

INTRODUCTION

Herbal medicines are plants or parts of plants that have been transformed into phyto-pharmaceuticals by simple gathering, harvesting, drying, and storage methods. Herbal medicines are the oldest type of medicine known to man, and they have been utilised for ages by people of all cultures. Since ancient forebears realised their need for nature for a healthy life, humanity has relied on a huge variety of plant sources for nourishment, shelter, clothes, and medication to treat a wide range of diseases.

Nature, taste, and experience encouraged Mesopotamian clay tablet writing and Primitive men and women to heal illnesses using plant, animal, and mineral components that were not commonly eaten.

Experimentation taught primitive humans how to distinguish between beneficial plants with beneficial effects and inactive or hazardous plants, as well as the processing procedures or combinations to use to get the greatest outcomes.

SYNONYMS	:	SAUPH
BIOLOGICAL NAME:		FOENICULUMVULGARE MILL
FAMILY	:	UMBELLIFERAE
KINGDOM	:	PLANTAE
GENUS	:	FOENICULUM
SPECIES	:	F. VULGARE

Habitat— Fennel is a tough, annual, umbelliferous plant with yellow flowers and fluffy foliage that grows naturally in most regions of continental Europe. It is native to the Adriatic coasts, from which it extends east to India. It has followed society, particularly wherever Italians have colonized, and may be seen growing wild on different areas of the universe in semi arid soils along seashores and riverbanks. It grows well on limestone soils and has become naturalized in several regions of the nation. It can be seen throughout North Wales to Kent, with the highest concentrations in Devon and Cornwall, as well as on chalk cliffs near the sea. It is frequently found in semi-wild condition in calcareous regions downstream.

Description

Fig 1 : Fennel fruits

Fennel is a pretty shrub. It will have a strong, annual root, robust stalks that are four to five feet in length, upright and tubular, brilliant emerald and so silky that they appear finished, and many branching leaflets that are sliced through into tiniest of sections. The golden yellow petals, which bloom in July and August and are developed in big, flat ending inflorescences with 13 to 20 beams, are developed in huge, shallow termination inflorescence.

CULTIVATION

Fennel can be cultivated practically anywhere and can last for years. Seeds, put in damp soils early in April, are a simple method to distribute it. It prefers bright sunshine and may thrive in

dry, sunny environments. It does not require a lot of organic manure in the soil, but it will yield more on thick, hard ground. With an annualised rate of 15 cwt. per hectare, this fruit is considerable. Fennel roots are occasionally used in medicine, but the fruit, which is the only portion approved by either of the Pharmacopoeias, is usually preferable in terms of quality.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Fennel is not consistent in composition when purchased. Fennel produces 4 - 5% essential oil (sp. gr. 0.960 to 0.930), its main components of those are Anethol (50-60%) and Fenchone (40-50%). (18 - 22 per cent). Anise oil also contains Anethol as a major component. Fenchone is a colourless gas with a strong, camphoraceous odour & flavour that provides several industrial oils an unpleasant bitter flavor when available.

METHOD and MATERIAL

Raw Material Collecting and Identification

Collected four batches of *Foeniculum vulgare* Mill. fruits from the Herbal Garden of S. D. College Of Pharmacy And Vocational Studies, Muzaffarnagar and authenticate from Botany department of Chotu Ram P.G. College Muzaffarnagar.

STUDIES ON PHARMACOGNOSY

Macroscopical studies- Macromolecular fundamental studies concentrate on large segment qualities that are difficult to detect with traditional methods.

Microscopy- Cross-sections of Fennel show a pentagonal mericarp, with four of the edges nearly equal and marginally sunken, the other or commissural surface being significantly longer and only the end of the root or less undulate; cells of the seed-cover firmly joined with those of the pericarp, giving the part two extremely distinct regions, the internal and larger piece (endosperm) pretty much adjusted pentagonal and fairly rhombic.

Powder microscopy Fennel Fruit Endosperm Powder Microscopy: Endosperm particles were plentiful and are made up of irregular tough outer walls cells having attached lipid granules and aleurone granules. Micro-rosette grains of calcium oxalate can also be seen in those layers.

PHYSIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Loss on drying

The Loss on Drying Study is used to determine how much aqueous and aromatic materials are present in a solution of sample after it has been dehydrated beneath specific circumstances. A statement like "not more than 0.50 percent (104 percent, 180 minutes)" inside the Pharmacopoeia means that weight reduction is not more than 0.50 percent of the sample as evaluated by drying 1.5 to 3 g of the sample, correctly measured, at 105o for 180 minutes. A description like "not more than 0.50 percent (0.5 g, not more than 1.3kPa, 24 hours)" means

that the weight reduction is not more than 0.50 percent of a specimen when measured besides simply putting approximately 0.50 g of the sample, correctly weighed, inside a desiccator with silica gel as the dehumidifier & dried under pressure of 1.3kPa and not less for 24 hours.

Ash Value:-

Ash determination

After ignition the remaining material is known as ash. There are two types of ash one is the ash derived from plant tissues (physiological ash) and the other one is remaining part of dust or soil material which adhering to plant surface (non-physiological ash).Ash will be determined by following three methods-

Total ash

- The mass of the ash is carried out after it has been ignited.
- A uncoated silicon crucible is filled with around two gm of granular substance.
- Inside a muffle furnace, burned at 450°C till it will be carbon-free.
- The crucible let remain cool and weighed the substance.
- % of total ash was calculated with air-dry substance.
-

Formula for the total Ash value determination-

Total Ash value of the given sample = $100 (A-B) \% / C$

Where,

A = weight of empty crucible,

B = weight of the given drug sample,

C = weight of the crucible + ash (after complete incineration).

Phytochemical Evaluation

Successive extraction- Fennel seeds are distilled using crude ingredients as from Cepogo District in Boyolali, Indonesia. This uses 5 kg of materials with black beans that are 0.3 mm long and have a particular flavour. 5 kg fresh fennel seeds were added to the pure water inside the pot.

The reason for implementing the dissolution rate of fennel seed oil in alcohol would be to assess the concentrations of volatile oil obtained from anise extraction process. This is accomplished by placing 2 ml of fennel oil inside a glass container, adding ninety percent ethanolic extract, and shaking the mixture until it is fully mixed. The ethanol is gradually added to generate a real solution and until the proportion of fennel oil and alcohol equals 1:3. The chemical contents of fennel seed oil are determined using GC-MS, and the metal content of fennel seed oil refined products is determined using AAS.

Qualitative Phytochemical analysis-

Anethole (between 42–71%)

Fenchone (between 3–21%)

Estragole (between 3–8%).

A portion of one isolated volatile oils (0.1 mL) mixed with dichloromethane (10 mL) and appropriate samples prepared in organic solvents were used for TLC analysis of *Foeniculum vulgare*. The samples are placed on a pre-coated Bayer silica gel plate (80, GF254, 250m) and grown across a 10 cm path with a 93:7 cyclohexane/Ethyl acetate solvent solution. UV light (254 nm) and H₂SO₄ at 140 °C for 3-6 minutes were used to detect these stains. The spots were initially seen under UV light (254 nm), and then at 140 °C for 5 minutes with H₂SO₄ in a second solvent solution (5:1 hexane / methylene chloride).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Macroscopic examination of *Fennel Fruit*:-

Table 1. Macroscopical Characteristics

S.No	Property	<i>Foeniculum vulgare mill</i>
1	Colour	Dark Green
2	Odour	Pleasant
3	Taste	Sweet
4	Size	4-10 mm long
5	Shape	Cylindrical
6	Surface characteristics texture	Hard

Table 2- Microscopic examination of Fennel fruit:-

Sr. No.	Constituents	Procedure for test/reagent	Result
1.	Starch crystals, Hemicellulose	Take a Spoon of Crude drug + 2 Drop of Iodine Solution	Blue colour
2.	Mucilage	Ruthenium Red	Pink colour
3.	Lignin	T.s. of crude drug + 1 drop of phloroglucinol + 1 drop of HCL	Pink colour

Observation with microscope, cross over segments of Fennel show a pentagonal mericarp, four of the edges being almost equivalent and marginally sunken, the other or commissural surface being significantly longer and that's only the tip of the iceberg or less undulate; cells of the seed-cover firmly joined with those of the pericarp, giving the part two extremely particular regions, the internal and bigger piece (endosperm) pretty much adjusted pentagonal and fairly reniform, made out of polygonal cells, loaded up with aleurone grains containing rosette totals of calcium oxalate and a meager protoplasmic layer encasing a decent oil;

The external or pericarp layer recognized by huge circular vittae with thick, earthy colored dividers, happening independently and rotating with the essential ribs, and two vittae on the dorsal surface, making typically six vittae taking all things together, happening independently and substituting with the essential ribs, and two vittae on the dorsal surface, making generally six vittae taking all things together, there now and then being, not withstanding, a couple vittae extra; in the focal piece of every one of the ribs happens an almost roundabout, fibro-vascular pack with a couple tracheae and various flimsy walled, firmly lignified sclerenchymatous filaments.

Fig 1.2 -Microscopy of Fennel

Evaluation of Physical Parameter

Determination of Total Ash

Name of Compound	Total Ash
Fennel	8.46

Table 3: Observation of Total Ash

By deducting the entire weight of a crucible and also the weight of the ash from the weight of the empty crucible, the total ash of the plant was estimated. The overall ash content of the FoeniculumVulgare mill was discovered to be 8.46% w/w.

Determination of Acid-Insoluble Ash

Table 4: Observation of Acid Insoluble Ash

Name of Compound	Acid Insoluble Ash
Fennel	0.97

The insoluble ash of the plant was performed and calculated by subtracting total ash from wweight of crucible and weight of acid insoluble ash. The acid insoluble ash of *Foeniculumvulgare mill* was found to be 0.97% w/w.

Determination of Water soluble ash

Table 5: Observation of water Soluble Ash

Name of compound	Water soluble ash
Fennel	4.36

Loss on Drying:-

Table 6: Observation of Loss on Drying

Name of Compound	Loss on drying %w/w
Fennel	9.60

Determination of Water extractive value

Table 7: Determination of Water extractive value

Name of Compound	Water extractive value %w/w
Fennel	20.46

Determination of pH:

pH was evaluated by using the polyherbal solution (1%) in the distilled water and pH is determined by using Systronic Digital pH meter that is 6.60.

Phytochemical screenin:

Successive extraction of the dried fine powder of the plant were done using different suitable solvent. The extract were dissolved in dil. Hcl and then perform the various test as mentioned in the table below with results.

Table 5.7: Various Chemical tests

S. No.	Name of test	Pet. Ether extract	Chloroform extract	Ethanollic extract
1.	Alkaloids	--	--	--
2.	Carbohydrates	++	++	++
3.	Phenolic compounds	++	--	++
4.	Flavonoids	++	++	++
5.	Saponins	++	--	++
6.	Steroids	++	++	++
7.	Glycosides	++	--	++
8.	Proteins	--	+	+
9.	Amino Acids	++	++	--
10.	Resins	--	++	--

CONCLUSION

Numerous research were conducted on the sample, including morphological, pharmacognostic, phytochemical, and physiochemical tests.

Based on the findings of the preceding studies, we can conclude that the parameters defined for the standardisation of *Foeniculum vulgare* are effective enough to be considered by the quality control department in order to ensure that the finished product consistency is maintained from batch to batch.

According to a literature study, the plant in the drug have Physiological properties. As a result, it was established that the drug had a substantial anti-anxiety and anti-anxiety behaviour impact.

More research is needed to determine the pharmacological and chemical characteristics of the formulation in order to determine the precise mechanism of action of the formulation and isolate the active principles responsible for these types of activities.

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